

Analytical study learners' articulatory difficulties in reading at primary school

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Abstract— In Burkina Faso, French is taught and learned at primary school through a variety of subjects such as oral expression, written expression, grammar, conjugation, spelling and reading. As far as reading is concerned, it has been found that learners have a variety of problems during reading sessions. They have difficulty with articulation and pronounce sounds and words incorrectly. So, what is the typology of articulation difficulties in reading and what explains this poor pronunciation of sounds and words? The aim of the study is to analyse the factors associated with this dysfunction in pupils in the early stages of their schooling. In our mixed-method approach, we opted for field surveys. This was done through audio recordings and observation of learners reading texts. Analysis of the corpus revealed that learners were confronted with articulatory difficulties in reading, manifested by word distortion and poor diction. Strategies were proposed to remedy these reading pronunciation difficulties.

Keywords— *pronunciation ; phonetics ; phonology ; segmentation ; suprasegmentation.*

I. INTRODUCTION

At primary school, French is taught through a number of subjects, including reading. Indeed, mastery of reading is essential because it is the primary condition for success at school. It is even an instrumental subject, because it is a prerequisite for learning other subjects. It enables students to extend the range of knowledge they have already acquired. The French Official Instructions of 20 June 1923 recognized the fundamental importance of reading at school, stating that “children can learn nothing if they cannot read”. In the same vein, A. Bentolila et al ^[1] (1993, p. 22) agree that knowing how to read is “the key to everything” and that failure to learn to read seriously compromises a child's future at school and often his or her social future. What emerges is that at the start of the learning process, some learners present a variety of problems during reading sessions. These learners have difficulty deciphering words and understanding their meaning. In view of the importance of reading in pupils' school careers, we have decided to make the articulatory difficulties of primary school reading learners the subject of this article. The study attempts to answer the following questions: What is the typology of pronunciation errors encountered by primary school reading pupils? What are the sources of articulatory difficulties with French sounds and words in primary school learners? The hypotheses arising from these questions are as follows: Some learners have enormous difficulties in pronouncing certain sounds when learning to read. The mispronunciation of sounds in pupils from CP to CM1 is due to the distortion of words and poor diction. The general aim of this study is to analyse the reasons why learners have difficulty pronouncing certain sounds in French at primary school. Specifically, the aim is to identify the typology of pronunciation errors in reading at the segmental and suprasegmental levels and to detect the sources of mispronunciation of sounds by learners, and finally, to propose teaching strategies with a view to remedying learners' mispronunciation in reading. The present study falls within the field of foreign language didactics, and more specifically that of French. However, the analysis is based on phonetics and phonology.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

To compile our corpus, we adopted a mixed methodological approach, i.e. quantitative and qualitative. We carried out field surveys related to difficulties in learning to read at primary school. An observation grid and audio recordings were used as data collection instruments. The field of study was the Sakoula-Est school in the Basic Education District of Ouaga IX in the province of Kadiogo. The target population consisted of pupils in CP1, CP2, CE1, CE2 and CM1 classes, where we randomly selected 10 pupils per class. The CP1 class was then given a reading text of vowels, words and short sentences. For the other classes, we read the following texts: “Premier jour de classe” for the CP2 class, “Le voleur de poisson” for the CE1 class, “Le singe, la tortue et le chien” for the CE2 class and “Enfant, que vas-tu faire à l'école?” for the CM1 class. This gave us an audio corpus of 50 recordings, which we then transcribed for analysis.

A second data collection tool was used. This was an observation grid. The learners in each class read aloud a text adapted to their level, and with this tool we checked their mastery of prosodic elements such as intonation, flow and duration. The choice of text for each class was justified by the fact that it was rich in interrogative, exclamatory and declarative sentences. The observation grid included criteria which enabled us to identify pronunciation problems in the learners, at the suprasegmental level, such as accentuation, intonation and rhythm. All these investigations, using the two tools mentioned above, provided information on the pronunciation deficiencies of primary school reading learners.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Typology of Learners' Pronunciation Errors in Reading

According to J.-P. Cuq ^[2] (2003, p. 183), "pronunciation is an action linked to articulation, but also to hearing (sensory capacity of the ear) and perception (interpretation of physical reality). Pronunciation therefore means hearing and producing the sounds and prosodic facts of a given language in such a way that a native speaker can understand the message addressed to him or her, or in such a way that pronunciation does not hinder communication between native and non-native speakers".

The recordings and classroom observations revealed four types of pronunciation error encountered by learners in reading. These are errors affecting the syllable, the word, the link and the prosody.

3.1.1. Pronunciation Errors Affecting the Syllable

According to J. Dubois ^[3] (1999, p. 45), "the syllable is the fundamental structure which is the basis of any grouping of phonemes in the spoken chain". Incorrectly pronouncing a syllable can lead to communication problems, such as altering the meaning of the word or sentence in which it is used. Pronouncing a syllable incorrectly can also affect the flow of conversation and disrupt the natural rhythm of speech and reading. These distortions are characterised by omissions, additions or substitutions of phonemes.

With regard to omissions of phonemes in the syllable, several omitted phonemes were found in the corpus in all classes. For example, the following syllables were strongly affected by the omission of one or more phonemes:

1. **Paticia** et Sanimata sont en classe. (CP2) ;
2. Tous ze élèves **dépo** les fournuré sous les ardoises **evant** eux. (CP2) ;
3. Cetin nuit, il y a un bon **clai** de line/lin/mune/lutte. (CE1) ;
4. Ma mère fait/fine/fule au coton **pès** du feuille. (CE1) ;
5. Es sais, nous sommes des annemis, le singe sera content de me voir morne et, pour se **venge**, il voudrait **joue** avec mon corps. (CE2) ;
6. Tout en tournant les passages tassés de noir, n'**etendez**-vous pas un prisement/bruit confé de voix vune de je ne sans où du fond des abîner/abîmés des sièches/sercle/saicle passés. (CM1).

In sentence 1, the word "Paticia" was mispronounced and this affected the 2nd syllable "ti" in which the phoneme /r/ was omitted. This omission altered the correct pronunciation of the word "Patricia". In the second sentence, the word "dépo" was mispronounced. In this word, the last silent syllable "sent", which contains the phonemes /s/, /e/, /n/ and /t/, was omitted. These omissions have altered the correct pronunciation of the word "déposent". In the same sentence, the word "evant" was also mispronounced, affecting the first syllable "e" in which the phoneme /d/ was omitted. As a result, this omission altered the correct pronunciation of the word "devant". In sentence 3, the phonemes /r/ and /e/ in the last syllable "re" were omitted from the word "clai". This resulted in a mispronunciation of the word "claire". In the fourth sentence, the word "pès" was mispronounced. This mispronunciation affected the word "pès" resulting in the omission of the phoneme /r/ with an alteration in the correct pronunciation of the word "près". The words "venge" and "joue" in sentence 5 were mispronounced. These mispronunciations affected the last syllables "ge" and "e" in which the phoneme /r/ was omitted. It is these omissions that have altered the correct pronunciation of the words "venger" and "jouer". In sentence 6, the word "étendez" was mispronounced, resulting in a mispronunciation of the first syllable "e" in which the phoneme /n/ was omitted. This omission altered the correct pronunciation of the word "entendez".

A number of observations emerge from these examples. The omission most often concerns consonant phonemes, except in sentence 2 where several phonemes have been omitted, including the vowel phoneme /e/. These omissions have a clear impact on the syllable, which loses its primary meaning while also affecting the comprehension of the word. With these omissions of letters, the new words produced by the learners lead to confusion and become nonsense for the interlocutor.

As far as the addition of phonemes to the syllable is concerned, clumsiness affects both consonantal and vowel phonemes. The examples below are illustrative.

7. Est et premier jour de **nannée nescolaire/escolaire**. (CP2) ;
8. Elle veut vous faire de belles **habite**/claire tour la fête de villaze. (CE1) ;
9. Il **voudrait** joue avec mon corps. (CE2) ;
10. Je le **laisserais** faire un moment puis je **bondirais** sur lui. (CE2).

In sentence 7, the word “nannée” was misarticulated and this affected the first syllable “na” in which the phoneme /n/ was added. This addition altered the correct pronunciation of the word “année”. Also in this sentence, the words “nescolaire” and “escolaire” were mispronounced. These mispronunciations affected the first syllables “nesco” and “esco”, in which the phonemes /n/ and /e/ in the word “nescolaire” and the phoneme /e/ in the word “escolaire” were added. The addition of these phonemes altered the correct pronunciation of the word “scolaire”. In sentence 8, the pronunciation of the word “habite” was altered. This mispronunciation had an impact on the second syllable “bite”, in which the phoneme /e/ was added. This addition altered the correct pronunciation of the word “habit”. In sentence 9, the word “voudrait” was affected by the mispronunciation of the second syllable “drait”, in which the phonemes /i/ and /t/ were added. It is these additions that have altered the correct pronunciation of the word “voudra”. In sentence 10, the words “laisserais” and “bondirais” were mispronounced. These mispronunciations affected the 3rd syllable “rais” of “laisserais” and “bondirais” respectively, in which the phoneme /s/ was added. This addition distorted the correct pronunciation of the words “laisserai” and “bondirai”.

The above-mentioned additions to sentences indicate learners' inability to read all commonly used words correctly, as is the case in example 7 with the word school, where the phoneme /s/ is pronounced as a hiss at the beginning of the sentence, but learners pronounce it as “es”. This phenomenon is specific because it does not occur when the /s/ phoneme is placed in the middle of a word. Also in example 7, some learners who are unable to pronounce the [s] sound at the beginning of a word combine it with other letters to achieve an easy and simple pronunciation of this sound. This is the case in “nescolaire” with the addition of the phoneme /n/. There is also a great deal of confusion about the endings of verbs conjugated in the future tense, which most learners use in the conditional tense, as in “je laisserais” and “je bondirais”. In addition, some learners confuse the persons of the conjugation, which also creates a confusion between the different endings. This is the case with the verb “laisser”, which is conjugated in the future simple tense in the first-person singular, but which was made with an “a” at the end as if it were the third person singular. In middle school, pronunciation difficulties are most often found in words containing several syllables. The various changes made to words affect the syllables by altering the meaning of the words in which they are contained. In this case, most errors occur in the last syllables of words that learners articulate incorrectly.

As far as phoneme substitution in the syllable is concerned, several variants were found in the following corpus:

11. Patricia et **Sanimata** sont en classe. (CP2) ;
12. **Ses** camarades et **toi**, nous **zouons** à **casse-casse**. (CE1) ;
13. Le **sien** qui avait envie depuis longtemps d'attraper le **sinze** dit alors à la tortue : **bèche des darmes**. (CE2) ;
14. Ce sont des morts qui parlent sans que **désormais** chaque force puisse faire taire les paroles... (CM1) ;
15. Je vais voir circule par les canaux jusqu'à dans les **repris** du cerveau le feuille rouge de **chang**. (CM1).

In sentence 11, the learner articulated “Sanimata” instead of “Salimata” and thus replaced the phoneme /l/ with the phoneme /n/ in the 2nd syllable “ni”. This substitution altered the pronunciation of the word “Salimata”. In sentence 12, the mispronunciations affected the first syllables “ses”, “toi” and “zou” in which the phonemes /m/ and /z/ were replaced by the phonemes /s/, /t/ and /z/. Also, the 2nd syllable “che” in which the phoneme /ʃ/ is found was affected by its substitution by the phoneme /s/. These substitutions altered the correct pronunciation of the words “mes”, “moi”, “jouons” and “cache-cache”. In sentence 13, the articulatory errors were due to the fact that the phonemes /ʃ/, /z/, /s/, /t/ and /l/ were replaced by the phonemes /s/, /z/, /b/ and /d/, and were respectively realised as “sien”, “sinze”, “bèche”, “des” and “darmes”. These substitutions altered the correct pronunciation of the words “chien”, “singe”, “sèche”, “tes” and “larmes”. In sentence 14, the pronunciation error in the word “désormais” is due to the fact that the learner replaced the phoneme /m/ with the phoneme /n/ to make “désornais”. In sentence 15, the articulation of the words “repris” and “sang” was affected by the learner's substitution of the phonemes /l/ by /r/ and /s/ by /ʃ/, resulting in the realisations “repris” and “chang” respectively.

In the various illustrations of substitutions, anteriorisation phenomena are by far the most frequently found errors in the corpus. These anteriorisation phenomena were found in several learners. The examples found mainly concern the phoneme /ʃ/, which is substituted by the anterior constrictive /s/. From an articulatory point of view, these two segments differ in their point of articulation. The /ʃ/ is articulated a little further back from the palatal vault and with the apical part. The articulation point of /ʃ/ is therefore prepalatal, as opposed to /s/, which is alveolar. These two consonants can also be distinguished acoustically by

the degree of constriction and turbulence produced in the oral cavity. Both articulatory and acoustic phonetic data suggest that /ʃ/ is more difficult to produce than /s/. Substituting /s/ for /ʃ/ therefore results in the production of a segment that is easier to produce phonetically. The sounds [ʃ] and [ʒ] are among the most difficult to pronounce. Learners frequently replace them with [s] and [z], which are very similar and are also easier for them to produce.

3.1.2. Pronunciation Errors Affecting the Word

Beyond the typology of pronunciation errors affecting the syllable, there are those affecting the word, to different degrees and at different levels. According to C. Fairon and A.-C. Simon^[4] (2018, p. 107), “the word is the basic unit of our grammatical system. It is made up of a series of sounds (or letters in writing), carries a meaning and plays a particular role in the sentence in which it is inserted”. During the reading, we noted that most learners in all classes did not render certain words correctly. In the examples below, several words were pronounced in their entirety, resulting in words that do not exist in French.

16. Tous **ze** élèves dépo les fournituré sous les ardoises evant eux. (CP2) ;
17. Ma mère **fait**/fine/fule **au** coton pès du **feuille**. (CE1) ;
18. **Cetin** nuit, il y a un bon **clai** de line/**lin/mune/lutte**. (CE1) ;
19. **Lavais** me coucher sur le dos, les **zi** fermes, et tu vas me **terné** par une datte juste au samp du sinze. (CE2) ;
20. N'étendez-vous pas un **prissement**/bruit confé de voix **vune** de je ne sans où du fond des abîner/abîmés des **sièches/sercle/saicle** passés. (CM1).

In sentence 16, the poor articulation of the determiner “les” affected the whole word, resulting in a complete change to the root of the word. Preoccupied with the link, the learner skipped the word “les” and went straight to the link between “les” and “élèves”. This change altered the correct pronunciation of the word “les”, leading to a misunderstanding of the meaning. In sentence 17, the incorrect articulation of the words “file”, “du” and “feu” affected these words through several phonemes which were either substituted, omitted or added. This is the case with the word “fait”, in which the phoneme /a/ has been added and the phoneme /l/ substituted by the phoneme /t/. As for the word “au”, the phoneme /d/ was substituted by the phoneme /a/. As for the word “feuille”, we note the addition of three phonemes /i/, /l/ and /e/. In sentence 18, the words “cetin”, “lin”, “mune” and “lutte” were poorly articulated by the CE1 learners. These articulation errors led to a modification of these words, thereby undermining their original meaning. This is the case with the words “cetin”, in which phonemes such as /t/, /i/ and /n/ have been added and omitted. In the 2nd word “lin”, the phoneme /u/ has also been replaced by /i/ and the phoneme /e/ omitted. In the word “mune”, the phoneme /l/ was substituted. This substitution affected the word “mune”, resulting in a complete deformation of the word. With the 4th word “lutte”, the phoneme /n/ was substituted by the phoneme /t/. These changes altered the correct pronunciation of the words “cette” and “lune”. In sentence 19, the words “je vais”, “yeux” and “traîné” were respectively articulated as “lavais”, “zi” and “terné” and this led to their total modification. With the word “lavais”, the phonemes /ʒ/ and /e/ were replaced by the phonemes /l/ and /a/. As for the word “zi”, it has been completely modified by the substitution of the phonemes /i/, /e/, /u/, /x/ by the phonemes /z/ and /i/. With the word “terné”, we also have substitutions of phonemes with other. In sentence 20, the words “bruissement”, “venue”, “sais” and “siècle” were pronounced “prissement”, “vune”, “sans” and “saicle”. These mispronunciations are due to the fact that the learner has either replaced, omitted or added phonemes. In the word “prissement”, the phoneme /b/ has been replaced by the phoneme /p/ and the phoneme /y/ has been omitted. In “vune”, the phoneme /e/ has been replaced by the phoneme /y/ and the phoneme /y/ has been omitted. In “sans”, the phoneme /i/ has been replaced by the phoneme /n/. With “saicle”, we note additions with the phoneme /a/ and omissions with the phoneme /e/. These various modifications have had an impact on the correct pronunciation of each of these words.

In light of these articulatory errors, the mispronunciation of a word can lead to a misunderstanding on the part of the interlocutor and lead to misunderstandings. Learners, in this way of pronouncing words, have altered the meaning of the words by rendering the sentences in which they are used obsolete. This harms the credibility and confidence of the speaker, because it is perceived as a sign of lack of linguistic knowledge. This misarticulation can also impact the way the interlocutor perceives the speaker. This is the case with the words “zi”, “terné”, “saicle”, etc. These words such as articulated, lead to a complete deformation of the sentences and therefore, give rise to a misunderstanding of the statement. These words have undergone a total modification thus affecting the primary meaning of the sentences. Taken in isolation, they have no meaning and even integrated into a sentence they give a different connotation than what is expected. In the middle course, it appears that even after 5 years of familiarization with the language of learning which is French, many learners continue to experience enormous difficulties in pronouncing the words and sounds of this language.

The analysis of these gaps suggests that they are no longer related to the deciphering of words, nor to the combination of syllables to form the word, but are of articulatory order. It is therefore important to pay attention to pronunciation given its importance in learning to read and in the process of understanding the message in oral communication.

3.1.3. Mispronunciation Affecting Liaison

“Liaison is a union in the pronunciation of the final consonant of a word, usually silent, with the initial vowel of the following word” (T. J. Natama ^[5], p. 77). Regarding liaison, surveys have revealed that the majority of learners omit it in the sequence of words. They read without paying attention to the liaison because they are unaware of what a liaison is and its importance in the accomplishment of good reading. Thus, in CP2, poor pronunciation affecting liaison and prosody are minimal. This is explained by the fact that in this course, learners are subjected to short sentences that rarely use liaison. In CE1, liaison is not so much affected because it is located in only one place: “de beaux habits”. Faced with this articulation, only three students were unable to correctly perform this liaison. In CE2, few cases of liaison occurred, because in the entire statement, there were only two cases of possible liaisons and these were optional. This is the case with the following expressions and structures: “dit alors” and “nous sommes des ennemis”. The majority of learners were able to produce these different liaisons without great difficulty. In CM, the majority of learners were able to produce the possible liaisons in the sentences. These liaisons are considered obligatory because they occur between determiners and nouns, between adjectives and nouns that follow. These were the following examples:

21. Petit enfant ;
22. Je vais apprendre à lire ;
23. Tout en tournant les pages ;
24. Je ne sais où ;
25. Des éclairs.

In example 21, the adjective “petit” is followed by the noun “enfant”. “Petit” ends with a silent consonant “t” and “enfant” begins with a vowel “e”. This is a mandatory liaison because the adjective is placed before the noun and ends with a silent consonant: “petit enfant” (pronounced: [pəti tāfā]). Failure to perform this liaison impacts the quality of the message. In example 22, the verb “vais” which ends with a silent consonant “s” is followed by the infinitive of the verb “apprendre” which begins with a vowel “a”. In this case, the liaison must be performed, because it is a mandatory liaison that is performed ([ʒə vɛ zaprɑ̃dr]). With example 23, “tout” is an adverb that ends with a silent consonant “t” and “en” is a preposition and begins with a vowel “e”. This association between an adverb and a preposition calls for a mandatory liaison and must be carried out by any good reader: “[tu tā]”. In example 24, the liaison is also mandatory between a verb ending with a silent consonant and the word that follows it. Failure to carry out this liaison affects the quality of the message. The correct realization will give the following pronunciation “je ne sais où” (pronounced: [ʒə nə sɛ zu]). In example 25, the determiner “des” which precedes the noun “éclairs” calls for a liaison: [dɛ zɛklɛʁ].

Overall, the analysis of the results reveals that learners have not mastered the rules and exceptions of liaisons and chaining learned in class. It is therefore obvious that these errors also affect prosody.

3.1.4. Mispronunciation Affecting Prosody

According to J. Vaissière ^[6] (2006, p. 97), “prosody refers to all aspects of speech not related to the identification of segments, in particular the facts of lexical stress, intonation, flow and rhythm”. It essentially refers to the study of the musicality of the language and contains a set of tools that contribute to good pronunciation of sounds. The majority of learners read without paying attention to prosody. As a result, many errors at the prosodic level, that is to say at the level of intonation, flow and pauses, have been noted. Thus, at the level of intonation, after the analysis of the audio recordings of the CE1 class, some learners read with a disrupted tone. Others produce an intonation that does not allow the different statements to be distinguished. In CE2, with regard to the intonation of sentences, the influence of the first language is very present. Most learners tend to emphasize the ends of each sentence even if they are not questions. In addition, generally speaking, an effort is made in the pronunciation of the isolated word, but very little when it is a group of words. In CM, to check whether learners mark the opposition between the types of sentences by the intonation realization (rising intonation for the interrogative sentence, falling for the declarative, rising for the exclamatory), a text with several types of sentences was chosen. It emerges from the realization of these sentences that the problem of intonation is quite adapted, because several learners manage to use the right tone in their expression. In terms of flow, the problem is less in comparison with pauses. Generally speaking, the majority of learners read aloud and intelligibly in almost all classes; a reading that allowed all learners to hear and understand what was being read. In terms of flow, all have a slow flow, that is to say less accelerated given the hesitations which do not allow a good understanding of the statement. Reading is rather sing-song and monotonous especially in the lower classes.

The flow rate can be fast, medium or slow. The flow rate problem is quite less compared to the other prosodic elements. Generally speaking, the learners had an average flow rate that allowed the realization of all possible demarcations and an understanding of the message by their interlocutors. However, in CE2, 4 learners had a fast flow rate that did not allow the understanding of the articulated message. As for pauses, they are ignored by the majority of learners in the small classes. In these classes, the learners do an almost mechanical reading without any respect for punctuation marks. There are some who make pauses, sometimes long, which mark hesitation. On the other hand, in the large classes, a minority of learners were able to pronounce well while making pauses that correspond to each type of sentence.

In short, the typology of pronunciation difficulties in reading is organized around errors affecting the syllable, the word, the liaison and the prosody.

3.2. Sources of Learners' Articulatory Difficulties

3.2.1. Sources of Articulatory Difficulties in the Preparatory Course

In CP1, reading aims to recognize and identify sounds, associate these sounds to form words, and decipher these words into syllables. This is the transformation of graphic signs into sounds, hence deciphering. In this class, many learners are unable to read the words in the text correctly. Of the 10 learners monitored, only three were able to read the text acceptably, and not without difficulty. This difficulty is explained by the fact that CP1 learners do not know all the letters. They are at the stage of discovering letters and sounds. At the time of recording the corpus, CP1 learners were studying the consonants “k” and “h”. They had already studied simple vowels, but not diphthongs. At this stage, their vocabulary is still poor and limited. They are not able to combine phonemes to syllabify difficult words. They cannot read all the words that contain new letters and sounds. Their reading is limited to vowels and single consonants and then to the combination of these to form syllables and words in one or two syllables.

In the preparatory course, the majority of learners (85%) have difficulty deciphering letters and making the associations necessary for acceptable fluent reading. This phenomenon is observed at three levels: those who have difficulty reading syllables, those who have difficulty reading words in the text and those who read without understanding what they are reading. For example, some confuse vowels, others, on the other hand, pronounce non-existent words in the text. They try to remember past sounds and often resort to their mother tongue, which results in faulty pronunciation, sometimes devoid of meaning. This situation is explained by the fact that it was January and the learners had not yet discovered all the phonemes and sounds planned to be studied in CP1. At this stage, they had just finished studying simple vowels and were beginning to study the first consonants, which will continue until mid-February. The study of diphthongs will be tackled just after that of the last consonants until the end of April. Finally, the study of compound articulations will take place in early May. If the program is followed correctly, by the end of CP1, learners should be able to read words, short sentences and short texts while speaking vowels, consonants and syllables. At this stage, the child is learning to pronounce sounds gradually. During learning, it is normal for some sounds to still be missing or for others to be distorted. It is generally accepted that by the age of 5 or 6, phonetics should be complete and all sounds mastered. Articulation difficulties may therefore be present early in the learner's development but may only be temporary difficulties.

At the start of CP2, learners will continue with the study of compound articulations, which will take them until February when they will move on to reading short sentences and short texts. It is important to note that the teaching-learning of reading in the early years of primary school is crucial, because it is the condition for accessing other school learning, other disciplines. This is why the French Official Instructions of June 20, 1923 specify that “a child cannot learn anything if he cannot read. He does not learn anything willingly if he cannot read easily”. Thus, at the end of CP, the student must be able to read words, short sentences and short texts while orally saying vowels, consonants and syllables. However, the observation that emerges is quite different, because for most learners, these skills are far from being established at the end of CP2. To this end, the results of the assessment of educational achievements (2014) showed that reading is successful at 14.2% in the First Year Preparatory Course (CP1) and at 46.8% in CE2. At the end of this assessment, we note that the reading situation is quite worrying, particularly in CP1.

3.2.2. Sources of Articulatory Difficulties in Elementary Course

Knowing how to read in CE and CM means going directly from the written sign to the meaning of the expressed thought. This is a skill that is acquired by learning fluent and expressive reading: reading aloud and understanding a text read. In CE1, learners' pronunciation difficulties are at the level of vowels, consonants but also at the level of flow, intonation and pauses. These pronunciation difficulties are explained by the fact that several learners interfere or tend to use habits specific to their mother tongue. For example, in Moore (a national language of Burkina Faso), the consonants “d” and “r” can alternate without altering the meaning of the word as in: “raaga/daaga” (market), “roogo/doogo” (house), etc.

The corpus revealed that at CE, the most common difficulties are, among others, the mixing of sounds, ignorance of the meaning of unknown words and the recognition of familiar words in a different context. 75% of learners have a defective pronunciation of words; this is manifested by articulatory errors at the level of vowels and consonants. At this level, decoding and deciphering are no longer the recurring problems of learners. The real problem lies at the level of the correct articulation of words. The difficulties are more accentuated at the level of diphthongs and compound articulations. Thus, the majority of learners tend to confuse the diphthongs “oi”, “on”, “eau”, “ai”, “en”, etc. in their reading and also at the level of compound articulations with the sounds “br”, “vr”, “gr”, etc. Also, there is a substitution of phonemes /s/ in place of the letters “ch” (“tassées/tachées”) and of the phoneme /z/ in place of the phoneme /ʒ/ with the word “zouons/jouons”. In reality, in this class, 60% of learners read mechanically. There is no respect for prosodic rules, namely intonation, liaisons, pauses and flow. Some learners read with a disturbed tone without respecting punctuation marks. This is a reading characterized by breaks, hesitations and difficulty in articulating certain sounds. The errors that recur among most learners concern intonation. Errors made when learning a new language are very often due to interference.

3.2.3. Sources of Articulatory Difficulties in Middle Course

In the CM, four learners tend to produce falling intonations in statements where the tone should be higher. As an illustration, we cite the production of the following sentence: [enfant que vas-tu faire à l'école↘] falling intonation indicating the purpose, instead of [enfant que vas-tu faire à l'école?] rising intonation at the level of the syllable [kol] indicating the question. Conversely, learners sometimes produce rising intonations, instead of falling intonations: [écoutez bien/] indicating continuity, instead of [écoutez bien//] which indicates the completion of the statement. Concerning rhythm, there are three learners who do not produce demarcations in rhythmic groups, that is to say, they produce few rhythmic accents and fewer pauses; On the other hand, there are others who make pauses, sometimes long, which mark hesitation, and a slow flow. In addition, some of them make redundancies and go back, they repeat a syllable 2 or 3 times before pronouncing a word. A minority of learners were able to achieve good pronunciation, with an intonation that corresponds to each type of sentence, pauses and an average flow.

In summary, learners generally made few distinctions in rhythmic groups: there were fewer stresses, few pauses, and misplaced intonations in their reading. This suprasegmental analysis reveals that poor intonation or intonation that is out of context could lead to a change in the meaning of what is said. Furthermore, the lack of distinction in rhythmic groups, particularly at the final syllable of each group, the absence of pauses, and the lack of variation in intonation pitch could also hinder the understanding of the message. It should also be noted that long and repetitive pauses, as well as a slow pace, could cause the speaker to lose the thread of their ideas and reduce the chance for the listener to grasp the meaning of the message. From a prosodic point of view, it remains important in the teaching and learning of a foreign language and can be summarized as follows: first, the learner-listener greatly benefits from taking prosodic cues into account to access meaning. In all languages, rhythm facilitates syntagmatic segmentation since pauses often appear at the boundaries of syntactic groups. Knowing how to interpret melodic movement can be essential for comprehension when intonation serves a modal function. It is intonation that allows distinguishing between two statements like “il fait beau.” and “il fait beau?”

Generally speaking, primary school learners encounter pronunciation difficulties, whether at the segmental or suprasegmental level. Some students have difficulty deciphering and pronouncing letters or sounds of the French alphabet. At the consonant level, confusion between letters is a major problem for many learners who cannot differentiate between the phonemes /p/, /b/ and /z/ and at the vowel level, the confusion is precisely at the level of oral vowels: [u], [ə], [ɛ], [ɔ], [y], [i]. Learners mainly confuse the rounded vowels [u] and [ə]. Analysis of the corpus shows that these errors are mainly due to the influence of the learner's mother tongue and also to the presence of certain sounds in French and their absence in the mother tongue.

Difficulties in pronouncing words during reading learning sessions among learners are manifested by the deformation of words and poor diction. Investigations have highlighted sources that are of various origins. The first source is linked to linguistic interference which is the result of the negative effect of the learner's first language on learning the second language. Also, the socio-cultural environment is also a cause of poor pronunciation among learners. The language stimulation that the student benefits from in his or her surroundings, from his or her immediate environment, has a significant impact on the way he or she pronounces and articulates words. Several strategies are developed in order to achieve better articulation of words and expressions in the French language.

IV. TEACHING PROPOSALS

The proposals are organized into two parts: suggestions for educational stakeholders and strategy proposals.

4.1. *Suggestions for Educational Stakeholders*

To the authorities in charge of basic education, in order to strengthen the capacities of educational supervisors and teaching staff, we suggest, in initial training, equipping all educational stakeholders with phonetics, phonology and contrastive analysis. To do this, it is a question of introducing a general linguistics module into the initial training curricula of primary school teachers within the National Institute for the Training of Teaching Staff. This module could also be integrated into the curricula of the Normal Superior School for the professional training of educational supervisors. The content of the phonetics and phonology course will allow them to master phonemes, graphemes and their correct pronunciation. Contrastive analysis will allow them to compare the sounds of the French language and the sounds of the language spoken by learners in order to anticipate pronunciation difficulties of certain phonemes of French that do not exist in our national languages. In continuing education, it is appropriate to periodically organize continuing education sessions for educational supervisors and teachers on themes that take into account the problem of reading. It would then be necessary to reinstate the Educational Animation Groups, the Refresher Courses and to boost the annual educational conferences. It is through these training frameworks that the most experienced will share their professional experiences in terms of teaching-learning strategies for reading with the less experienced. Regarding teaching materials, we suggest providing learners with reading manuals. Indeed, the current ratio recommended in the distribution of textbooks in primary school is one book for two learners. This ratio must be improved in order to provide each learner with a textbook to enable them to become familiar with written texts. Also, they will be able to use the textbooks at home to practice reading.

For teachers, we suggest that they:

- develop students' oral expression skills in order to facilitate reading, because the immense challenge for students is to learn to listen and speak French, at the same time as they must learn to read and write. Oral expression must therefore be made the gateway to learning to read;
- establish a “literate environment” within the classroom. For the teacher, this involves using the classroom walls and other supports such as posters, kraft paper and cardboard sheets and writing letters, words associated with images and sentences to make available and accessible to learners. This literate environment will allow them to quickly become familiar with the spelling and pronunciation of the most common words, thus facilitating their reading in texts;
- rigorously apply the teaching-learning methodology of reading from CP in order to facilitate the acquisition of different sounds and their different combinations to form syllables, then words and sentences while emphasizing correct pronunciation and associating the oral code with the written code;
- early identification of learners with particular difficulties in articulating certain sounds for differentiated support through practical exercises in pronouncing these sounds.

For parents of students, we suggest that they provide their children with reading manuals and various other books that can facilitate learning to read while encouraging them to have a taste for reading.

4.2. *Strategy Proposals*

Several strategies allow the remediation of poor pronunciation in learners. After detecting the most frequent pronunciation errors in learners, corrective work is necessary. As a result, several possible solutions could help improve the pronunciation deficit in learners. Indeed, the practice of reading aloud allows the correction of learners' pronunciation errors. In addition to reading aloud, reciting poems, practicing songs and role-playing games promote work on the musicality of the language, therefore on prosody, thus helping to minimize articulation difficulties. Listening and production exercises are also strategies for remediation of poor pronunciation in reading. For learners to have an easy and sonorous voice in oral reading, they must be offered special relaxation training during the preparatory exercises for learning to read. All these activities could provide the foundations for acquiring good pronunciation.

V. CONCLUSION

The objective pursued through this study was to analyze the reasons why learners have difficulties in pronouncing certain sounds in French in primary school. The analysis of the corpus revealed that many students have pronunciation difficulties in reading. These difficulties are a crucial problem that challenges all education stakeholders, because we cannot consider the quality of education if students cannot read. The investigations also highlighted the plausible sources of poor pronunciation in reading among learners. These are linguistic interference and the influence of the learners' socio-cultural environment. Almost all learners have a mother tongue other than French and there are sounds and syllabic patterns specific to each of these languages. In addition, pronunciation errors are manifested by the deformation of words and poor diction. Proposals for strategies were made to solve the problem of poor pronunciation of sounds by learners in reading. The educational authorities will need to strengthen the capacities of supervisors and teaching staff and provide learners with reading manuals. Teachers should do sufficient phonetic training with their learners in the classroom. As a perspective, it is necessary that further research be conducted on pronunciation difficulties in order to provide several remedial strategies to teachers for successful practice of teaching-learning reading.

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